

LOG BOOK

**The Influence of Blood Types on
Perceived Recovery from
Infectious Diseases Among
University Students in
Anuradhapura District, Sri Lanka**

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Unit Title	Applied Sciences Research Project		
Assignment Number		Assessor	
Submission Date		Date Received 1st submission	
Re-submission Date		Date Received 2nd submission	
Assessor Feedback:			
Grade: Assessor	Signature: Date:		
Resubmission Feedback:			
*Please note resubmission feedback is focussed only on the resubmitted work			
Grade:	Assessor Signature:		Date:
Internal Verifier's Comments:			
Signature & Date:			

Please note that grade decisions are provisional. They are only confirmed once internal and external moderation has taken place and grades decisions have been agreed at the assessment board.

Introduction

Title of the Research:

"The Influence of Blood Types on Perceived Recovery from Infectious Diseases Among University Students in Anuradhapura District, Sri Lanka."

Aim:

To investigate the influence of blood type on self-reported recovery outcomes from infectious diseases among university students in Anuradhapura District, Sri Lanka, using a survey and handwritten questionnaire-based approach, and to explore its potential applications in personalized healthcare and public health policy.

General Objective:

To examine the relationship between blood type and perceived recovery from infectious diseases among university students in Anuradhapura, and assess its implications for healthcare decision-making and personalized medicine.

Specific Objectives:

1. To determine the distribution of blood types among surveyed university students in Anuradhapura.
2. To analyze self-reported recovery experiences, including recovery time, severity, and treatment response, across different blood groups.
3. To identify patterns in healthcare-seeking behaviour (e.g., hospital visits, use of traditional medicine) based on blood type.
4. To assess whether patients and healthcare providers perceive blood type as a factor in disease recovery.
5. To explore how knowledge of blood type's influence on recovery could be applied in public health strategies and personalized medicine.

Hypotheses: Null**Hypotheses (H₀):**

- H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between blood type and perceived recovery from infectious diseases. • H₀₂: Blood type distribution does not significantly vary from population norms.
- H₀₃: No significant difference in healthcare-seeking behavior exists by blood type.
- H₀₄: Blood type is not perceived as a recovery factor. • H₀₅: Awareness of blood type impact has no influence on health policy or medicine.

Alternative Hypotheses (H₁):

- H₁₁: There is a significant relationship between blood type and perceived recovery. • H₁₂: Blood type distribution significantly varies from norms.
- H₁₃: Healthcare-seeking behaviour differs by blood type.
- H₁₄: Blood type is perceived as a recovery factor.
- H₁₅: Awareness of blood type impact influences health strategy and personalized care.

Methodology Overview:

- Study Design: Cross-sectional mixed-methods study (quantitative + qualitative)
- Population: University students (aged 18+) in Anuradhapura District
- Sample Size: ~374 students (questionnaires), ~40 for interviews • Tools Used: Google Forms, hand-distributed questionnaires, interviews
- Data Analysis:
 - Quantitative: Descriptive stats, chi-square tests
 - Qualitative: Manual Thematic Analysis
- Data Collection Period: 16th January 2025 to 15th July 2025
- Sampling: Stratified random sampling for quantitative; purposive for qualitative
- Ethical Approval: Secured from AIBS Campus
- Pilot Study: Conducted with 20 participants and revised based on feedback

Contact Details:

- ✉ Researcher Email:
- ✉ Supervisor Email:

Date	Task/Activity	Details & Reflections	Difficulties Faced	Solutions / Changes & Actions Taken
18/01/2025	Assignment Released	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Began exploring research areas based on personal interest and relevance. - Found the relationship between blood types and infectious disease recovery intriguing. - Aware of health relevance post-COVID19. - Considered scope in Sri Lankan context. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Topic felt too broad and unfocused. - Didn't specify target group or setting. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supervisor advised narrowing scope. - Decided to focus on university students in Anuradhapura District.
21/01/2025	Literature Search Started	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conducted search using Google Scholar, PubMed, ResearchGate. - Used keywords: “blood types,” “immunity,” “infectious disease,” “student population.” - Gathered 10+ international studies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited Sri Lankan context available. - Few studies related to students. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adjusted focus to university student demographic. - Included local terms and contexts in search.
25/01/2025	Research Gap Identified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Found a visible gap in literature linking blood types with perceived recovery in Sri Lankan students. - Most global research focused on hospital patients or general populations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No major difficulty, but validation needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Confirmed this gap with supervisor. - Justified the research with practical/local relevance.

<p>01/02/2025</p>	<p>Supervisor Meeting</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shared idea of linking blood types and student recovery perceptions. - Explained why university students are relevant due to knowledge/awareness and health-seeking behaviors. - Discussed feasibility of sampling. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - None reported. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supervisor approved refined scope. - Advised to begin proposal structure.
<p>04/02/2025</p>	<p>Scope Finalized</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Finalized title and objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - None. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Outlined aims and key research questions.
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clear aim: assess influence of blood types on recovery perception. - Selected Anuradhapura as geographical focus due to accessibility. 		
<p>07/02/2025</p>	<p>Methodology Planning</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chose quantitative approach with structured questionnaire. - Selected simple random sampling as method. - Justified with accessibility of student population. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unclear how to perform random sampling practically. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reviewed research methodology textbooks. - Asked supervisor to review draft design.
<p>10/02/2025</p>	<p>Proposal Writing Begins</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Drafted first sections: background, rationale, aims, and objectives. - Started mapping out structure: introduction, methodology, literature review. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Writing flow was challenging. - Unsure how to cite some references. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Referred to example proposals. - Used citation manager (Zotero).

12/02/2025	Hypotheses Formulated	- Developed null hypothesis (no relationship) and alternative hypothesis (blood type influences perceived recovery). - Ensured hypotheses matched research aim.	- Slight confusion on wording hypotheses properly.	- Used supervisor's examples and research textbook guidance.
15/02/2025	SPSS Basics Learned	- Practiced using SPSS with trial data. - Learned to enter variables, perform frequencies, and simple charts. - Focused on familiarity.	- Initially confusing interface. - Mistaken data entries.	- Used YouTube tutorials and trial runs. - Took notes for future reference.
18/02/2025	Literature Review Deepened	- Focused on recent studies about blood groups, susceptibility, and disease resistance. - Categorized findings based on type O, A, B, AB.- Noted findings related to COVID-19 and dengue.	- Lack of literature involving student populations . - Mostly hospitalbased studies.	- Decided to use international studies as base and highlight local gap.
20/02/2025	Proposal Continued	- Continued writing: literature review and methodology refined. - Connected theory to practical student health scenarios.	- Difficulty integrating references smoothly.	- Revised several drafts. - Received feedback from peer.
22/02/2025	Supervisor Proposal Feedback	- Supervisor highlighted sampling explanation needed clarity. - Recommended elaborating on ethical measures.	- Sampling rationale unclear. - Ethical plan too general.	- Rewrote sampling section with population data. - Expanded ethics portion to include consent and privacy.
25/02/2025	Final Proposal Sent	- Sent finalized proposal with refined structure and references.	- Minor citation mismatches.	- Doublechecked with Grammarly and citation software.

		- Formatted according to HND guidelines.		
28/02/2025	Ethics Form Submitted	- Filled research ethics form including:→ Purpose→ Consent→ Data security→ Participant rights	- Some sections confusing due to technical legal wording.	- Used institutional template. - Supervisor explained required changes.
05/03/2025	Ethics Approval Granted	- Received approval after review. - Suggested improvements already applied. - Cleared to proceed with data collection.	- None.	- Updated consent form as per feedback.
07/03/2025	Pilot Survey Conducted	- Conducted test with 10 students. - Asked for feedback on clarity and time. - Q5 found confusing.	- Ambiguity in Q5.- Layout too congested.	- Reworded Q5.- Added spacing in layout.
10/03/2025	Tool Revised	- Finalized revised survey with improved wording. - Added clearer instructions and simpler language.	- None.	- Reviewed with supervisor.
16/03/2025	Summative Proposal Submitted	- Submitted finalized version to meet deadline. - Included clear objectives, refined	- Short time frame for editing.	- Time managed with peer support and supervisor advice.
		tools, and literature support.		
20/03/2025	Tool Reviewed Again	- Supervisor reviewed revised survey. - Minor comments on format.	- None.	- Adjusted fonts and spacing for readability.

		- Content approved.		
22/03/2025	Tool Approved	- Ready for final distribution. - Prepared printed and Google Form versions.	- None.	- Began planning for rollout.
25/03/2025	Distribution Strategy Finalized	- Decided to use both physical and online forms. - Targeted multiple faculties for better sample diversity.	- Concern over low online engagement.	- Combined online and faceto-face methods.
28/03/2025	Printed Survey Design Finalized	- Improved physical survey design. - Ensured space for ticking/marking answers. - Clear fonts and layout.	- Initial layout had crowding.	- Used MS Word templates for layout correction.
01/04/2025	Online Survey Launched	- Shared Google Form through WhatsApp, Telegram, and university groups. - Asked friends to share.	- Initial responses were very low.	- Planned printed form circulation to boost numbers.
07/04/2025	Monitoring Responses	- Tracked daily response count. - Noted that Google Form had lower returns.	- Response rate lower than expected.	- Scheduled reminders via WhatsApp groups.
10/04/2025	Printed Surveys Prepared	- Printed 250 forms using university facilities. - Coordinated with printing staff.	- Minor delay due to printer queue.	- Requested early printing slot from admin office.
12/04/2025	Printed Distribution Begins	- Distributed forms during lecture breaks. - Explained research briefly to participants.	- Some students hesitant.	- Ensured anonymity and academic use only.

15/04/2025	Data Entry Started	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Began entering data into Excel. - Labeled columns clearly. - Double-checked entries. 	- Some typos and repeated entries.	- Used ID checklist and peer verification.
18/04/2025	Supervisor Check-in	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reviewed progress with data collection. - Online participation still poor. - Supervisor suggested focusing on in-person. 	- Online platform inefficient.	- Prioritized physical surveys.
22/04/2025	Distributed to More Faculties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reached Arts, Science, Management faculties. - Targeted both fulltime and weekend students. 	- Night-time students were harder to approach.	- Coordinated with class reps for distribution.
27/04/2025	Sample Update	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collected ~100 responses. - Input progress logged. 	- Still below target.	- Printed 150 more forms.
01/05/2025	Supervisor Meeting	- Discussed structure of dissertation chapters. - Supervisor explained flow: intro, methods, results, discussion.	- None.	- Began outline for thesis.
05/05/2025	Printed Survey Round 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reprinted surveys. - Engaged 3 peers to help with distribution. 	- Timeconsuming.	- Created schedule for each helper.
10/05/2025	Sample Count at 150	- Good improvement in responses. - Data now ~150 entries.	- Excel management became tiring.	- Shifted to Google Sheets for automatic saving.
15/05/2025	SPSS Testing with Sample Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Imported Excel data into SPSS. - Ran frequencies and crosstabs. - Practiced labeling. 	- Output had undefined values due to coding issues.	- Reviewed coding and cleaned variable names.

20/05/2025	Supervisor Check-in	- Supervisor reviewed SPSS files. - Suggested improving variable labeling for graphs.	- Unclear variable labels.	- Renamed variables with full words.
25/05/2025	Final Push for Sample Collection	- Personally approached hesitant students. - Explained benefits of participation.	- Some refused citing time issues.	- Offered quicker filling via tickbox method.
30/05/2025	Sample Count at 250	- Achieved 250 responses. - Confidence in reaching full target.	- None.	- Continued final collections.
04/06/2025	Final Printed Round Completed	- Last round of printed forms distributed. - Confirmed with students about deadline.	- Some students delayed return.	- Sent SMS reminders via peers.

07/06/2025	Final Data Entry Completed	- Finished all entries in SPSS. - Matched IDs, cleaned sheets.	- Duplicate IDs and errors.	- Used student ID as unique code.
10/06/2025	Data Cleaning	- Checked missing data, blanks, and duplicates. - Removed 5 incomplete entries.	- Some data had blank fields.	- Documented exclusions in appendix.
15/06/2025	Sample Reached = 374	- Final count: 374. - Target surpassed.	- None.	- Marked end of data collection phase.
20/06/2025	Supervisor Meeting	- Discussed types of analysis. - Supervisor recommended Chisquare test.	- Unsure of suitable test.	- Finalized analysis method for categorical data.
25/06/2025	Final Analysis in SPSS	- Ran Chi-square tests. - Created tables and graphs for results.	- None.	- Exported charts to Word.
27/06/2025	Drafting Results Chapter	- Wrote interpretation of analysis. - Linked results to research questions.	- Some terms unclear.	- Asked supervisor for clarification.

30/06/2025	Supervisor Feedback on Draft	- Feedback: improve grammar and formatting. - Some graphs too complex.	- Formatting errors.	- Used format guide to correct layout.
04/07/2025	Presentation Slide Design Begins	- Drafted 15 slides with summary of findings. - Added visuals and charts.	- Too much detail in slides.	- Reduced to 10 slides with key bullet points.
07/07/2025	Final Logbook Updated	- Updated logbook with all past activities. - Ensured complete reflection.	- None.	- Finalized and saved in printready format.
10/07/2025	Analysis Chapter Finalized	- Final version completed with charts and interpretations. - Linked with objectives.	- None.	- Ready for printing.
13/07/2025	Final Slides & Print Material Ready	- Printed full report, slides, and logbook. - Arranged copies for submission.	- None.	- Organised in folders.
15/07/2025	Project Submitted	- Submitted to department on time. - Felt relief and pride in final outcome.	- None.	- Submitted

2025/07/13

Date:

Supervisor Signature:

